
FIELD TRIPS AS A TEACHING STRATEGY: EFFECTS ON STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND ACHIEVEMENT IN CIVIC EDUCATION IN UYO, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study was conducted in secondary schools in Uyo Educational zone. The aim was to investigate the effects of field trip on secondary school students' motivation and achievement in civic education in Uyo educational zone, Nigeria. It was a quasi-experimental design involving 80 JSS3 students. Using cluster sampling method, two junior secondary schools were drawn from 125 junior secondary schools in the educational zone. In both schools, the children were taken on field trips to have firsthand experience on the various topics and concept of Civic Education. The instruments for data collection consisted of researcher-made "Rule of Law, Human Right, Citizenship, Civic Responsibility and Democracy Achievement Test" (RHCCDAT). It also consists of the "Students Motivation Inventory" (SMI). The instruments were vetted by experienced Civic Education teachers in secondary schools as well as the experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. The reliabilities of the instruments as determined using 20 JSS3 students with a test-retest sub-sectional reliability coefficient of 0.75, 0.82, 0.66, 0.75 and 0.81. Then the students were given a follow-up test after a period of two weeks. Data collected using the instruments were subjected to analysis using independent t-test as well as paired sample t-test. Result indicated that there was no significant effect of field trip on students' motivation ($p=0.091>0.05$). Field trip also had significant effect on students' achievement in Civic Education ($p=0.021<0.05$). Finally, there was a significant retention effect of field trip as there was no significant difference between the posttest and follow up test scores. Based on this, it was recommended among others that educational implementers like teachers, governments as well as the school should re-evaluate field trip objectives and design to focus on motivation.</p>	<p>field trip, motivation, academic achievement, civic education</p>

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in the development of any nation. Ukpon (2000) stated that globally, the extent to which education has develop or progress is always determined by both the specific and general academic capacity of students. Achievement is defined as “how well or badly one does something or how well or bad something works”. It is an act or process of performing a task, an action etc. it also involve an act involving a lot of efforts or trouble. To this note, Eze (1986) opined that academic achievement relates to the degree of performance students put towards academic success.

In educational institutions, success is measured by academic achievements or how well a student meets standards set out by governments and the institution itself. As career competition grows, ever fiercer in the working world, the importance of students doing well in school has caught the attention of parents, legislators and government education departments alike. Howard (2009) stated that in the past, academic achievements or attainments were often measured by ear than today. He stressed that teachers observations made up the bulk of assessment and todays summation or numerical method of determining how well a student is performing is a fairly recent invention.

Motivation serves as a fundamental driver influencing students' engagement and performance in senior secondary school physics. It encapsulates the internal and external forces that stimulate students' desire to learn, persist in the face of challenges, and achieve academic success in a subject often deemed complex and abstract. This concept of motivation extends beyond mere interest, involving a blend of emotional, cognitive, and social elements that together shape a student's academic journey (Adeyemo, 2022). Murray (2022) defines motivation as the desire to accomplish something difficult, overcome obstacles, attain a high standard, and excel in a given task. In the same vein, Byrne (2020) sees motivation as a learned motive to compete and strive for success. Also, Burger (2017) stresses that motivation is an individual desire to accomplish difficult tasks, overcome obstacles, attain high standards, and excel. At the heart of motivation is the idea that students' actions are guided by their intrinsic enjoyment of the subject and the extrinsic rewards they anticipate.

It is worth nothing that motivation on itself must be steered. It is not doubtful that some activities create motivation of students on something while other brings demotivation. Students are motivated to learn as a result of various factors and failure to explore these factors that causes adequate motivation to the students can be disastrous. According to Daramola (2013), when students are intrinsically motivated, they derive satisfaction from the learning process itself. This intrinsic motivation drives them to tackle challenging problems, persist through difficulties, and seek a thorough understanding of concepts. Again, a lack of motivation can lead to disinterest and disengagement, negatively impacting both immediate performance and future educational and career paths in physics-related fields. Students' differences in motivation to learn learning have often been related to some individual factors such as the technique of teaching itself.

Achievement in school is evaluated in a number of ways. For regular grading, students demonstrate their knowledge by taking written or oral test, performing presentations, turning in homework and participating in class activities and discussion. In the secondary school systems in Nigeria, Obinna (1998) noted that students are being evaluated through home works, assignments, test, examinations, etc. Students' academic achievements may serve as a motivator or demotivation to teachers. Karishma (2013) defines academic achievement as “something one does or achieve at school, college or university, in class, in a laboratory, library or fieldworks, which does not include sports or music” and examples of such include graduating or coming first position in class, having ones findings in research work being published by a recognized journal, having named as the head of a department of a university, are all academic achievements. With reference to students in the secondary schools, academic

achievement is realized when a student comes out with good grades in one sitting on his final year examination (i.e. WASCE or NECO) to enable him gain admission into the university.

Olusola (2023) had maintained that students' academic performance in different subjects has been a source of worry for stakeholders in education and civic education is not an exemption. It aims to help people learn how to become active, informed, and responsible citizens. RietbergenMcCracken (2004) stated that Civic education (also known as citizen education or democracy education) can be broadly defined as the provision of information and learning experiences to equip and empower citizens to participate in democratic processes. The education can take very different forms, including classroom-based learning, informal training, experiential learning, and mass media campaigns. According to Finkel (2000), Civic education can be targeted at children or adults, in developed or developing countries, and at the local, national or international level. As such, civic education is an approach that employs a range of different methods, and is often used in combination with other participatory governance tools. Rietbergen-McCracken (2004) also noted that Civic education is concerned with three different elements: civic knowledge, civic skills and civic disposition. Civic dispositions are defined as the citizen traits necessary for a democracy (e.g. tolerance, public spiritedness, civility, critical mindedness and willingness to listen, negotiate, and compromise). In totality, it refers to citizens' understanding of the workings of the political system and of their own political and civic rights and responsibilities (e.g. the rights to freedom of expression and to vote and run for public office, and the responsibilities to respect the rule of law and the rights and interests of others). Civic education was introduced as part of the basic education program for the purpose of developing young Nigerian people into responsible citizens (Federal Ministry of Education, 2007). Enu and Odey (2017) maintained that the Civic Education Curriculum is the pathway to realizing the successful political process direly needed in the country. Civic education is expected to inculcate the spirit of nationalism and desirable habits, values, and attitudes in students (Sheu & Eleana, 2020) and also to enhance the attainment of the objectives of education (Azebamwan, 2010).

According to Agbor, Bankong and Akong (2005), the type and pattern of instructional materials as well as the teaching method adopted in teaching the students plays a great role in the understanding of the students in any subject. Consequently, this infers that the level of academic achievement by students can be dependent on the type of teaching methods adopted.

Educators have over the adopted field trips as an important method or strategy in teaching students. Field trip according to Amosa, Ogunlade and Atobatele (2022) is a study trip taken outside the classroom to obtain direct experience from a natural setting. It is organized to improve students' interest in learning, for collecting data, materials or objects for classroom lessons as well as to observe objects or phenomena not possible to bring within the classroom. Field trip is a planned exercise taking place outside the four walls of the classroom. It offers opportunity for learners to get firsthand information on people, places and things for the permanency of learning experiences (Instructional Strategies Online, 2013). Field trip is a tour planned by teacher to benefit the student learning process. The trip is planned for learners to experience theory in practice.

Dasun, Ariya and Kazi (2023) maintained that the field trip technique is one of the techniques used in Social Studies that encourage firsthand knowledge of the students about the subject contents. It involves visits to places outside the regular classroom and allows students to discover things themselves. It is in line of this thought that Ganiyu (2016) revealed that the field trip technique is comprehensive, systematic, tasking and expensive. Thus, most teachers of secondary schools are lazy and not creative to put forward a plan for the field trip. Ogunlade (2017) observes that teachers have lukewarm attitude towards using field trip and that most teachers in all fields including Social Studies do not use the technique as required, this could be due to their attitude towards the

technique. The use of field trip in teaching and learning is often thought as leading to teacher _learner interaction outside the classroom (Amosa, Ogunlade & Atobatele, 2022). Such relations holds in a new learning environment and result in a meaningful teaching and learning process. Fakomogbon, Ibrahim, and Gegele (2007) noted that the basic technology curriculum requires child-centered and activity_oriented teaching and learning processes. Presently, it is important to use different teaching methods and learning processes as well as strategies to ensure student understanding. Since field trip is a method of teaching used to collect firsthand information in the course of investigation, this will enable both teachers and students to create meaningful and productive learning both on the field and in schools. According to Omosewo (2009), field trip can be used as a chance to collect data for later analysis, to generate artwork and stimulate discussions both on site and back at schools and universities in tutorials, seminars and workshops.

Again, it is believed that using field trip technique in teaching helps to bring about an effective learning of Civic Education. It is of enormous benefit because it enhances the observation of learning experiences in the field of engineering works where engineering materials such as plastic, ceramics, rubber, wood and metals are used. Field trips are an interactive method of teaching which give both male and female students equal opportunity to widen their practical and cultural experience by varying their learning environments. Thus, Amosa (2013) remarked that no evidence of superiority is expected to be noticed in the academic performance based on gender, if both males and females students are exposed to learning experiences equally.

In Uyo educational zone, academic achievement of students has over the years attracted much attention. This is evidence in the poor level of performance as well as fallen standard of students' academic achievements and attainments. The continuous repetition of classes by students and the significant low performance in general examinations are also pointers to this notion. Most people know that academic achievement generally refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her task and studies, but there are quite a number of factors that may determine the level and quality of students' academic achievement as noted by Bell (2011). It is noted that in spite of the relevance of civic education, secondary school students' academic achievement in the subject has continued to indicate a sharp decline (Dasun, Ariya & Kazi, 2023). Again, there is a continuous fluctuation in students' achievement in both internal and external examinations in the subject. This situation is evident in Uyo educational zone where there is a constant uncertainty in students' achievement in both standardized and teacher made examinations in civic education. This result may not be unconnected to the technique used in the teaching of the subject by teachers in the secondary school level. Based on this background, the aim of the study generally is to investigate the effect of Field Trip on Secondary School Students' motivation and achievement in Civic Education in Uyo

Educational Zone, Nigeria

Specifically, the study intended to;

1. Find out the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students as compared between the experimental and control group
2. Find out the effect of field trip on academic performance of students as compared between the experimental and control group scores.
3. Find out the retention effect of field trip on students' academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores.

The following research questions were asked in the course of the study;

1. What is the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students as compared between the experimental and control group?

2. What is the effect of field trip on students' academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores?

3. Does field trip have any retention effect of field trip on students' academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores.

The following hypotheses were also formulated in the course of the study;

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students when compared between the experimental and control group.

2. There is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on students' academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores.

3. There is no significant difference in the retention effect of field trip on students' academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in secondary schools in Uyo Educational zone. It was a quasiexperimental design involving 80 JSS3 students. Using cluster sampling method, two junior secondary schools were drawn from 125 junior secondary schools in the educational zone. In each school, two intact JSS2 classes were used comprising 20 participants in the experimental and 20 in the control group. Again, stratified non-proportionate sampling was used to draw twenty students from this intact class. This gave a total of forty (40) participants from each of the school and eighty (80) from the two schools drawn for the study. In both school, the children were taken on field trips to have firsthand experience on the various topics and concept of Civic Education. On the other hand, the controls groups were not taken on the trip but were just taught Civic education only in the classroom level. The experimental group was taken to important places of interest where resource persons took them round their establishments showing them what they needed to observe and learn about. In this way, they learned a lot of things in their natural settings. In the second school, the experimental group of 40 students were taught with lecture method. The units of Civic education topics taught to both the control and experimental groups during the period of the study were Rule of Law, Human Right, Citizenship and Civic Responsibility as well as Democracy. The instruments for data collection consisted of researcher-made "Rule of Law, Human Right, Citizenship, Civic Responsibility and Democracy Achievement Test" (RHCCDAT). It also consist of the Students Motivation Inventory (SMI). The "RHCCDAT" consisted of 30 multiple-choice objective items developed from the Rule of Law, Human Right, Citizenship, Civic Responsibility and Democracy topics covered during a four-week period of the treatment. On the other hand, the Students Motivation Inventory (SMI) was also designed using a 4-point Likert scale with twenty items that sought to measure the level of motivation of the students. The instruments were vetted by experienced Civic Education teachers in secondary schools as well as the experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. The reliabilities of the instruments as determined using 20 JSS3 students who did not participate in the main study and through the test-retest method and Pearson moment correlation technique were 0.75, 0.82, 0.66, 0.75 and 0.81 for Law, Human Right, Citizenship, Civic Responsibility and Democracy respectively. The posttest test was administered to the students and when they had responded to them, they were retrieved and scored. Then the students were given a follow-up test after a period of two weeks. Data collected using the instruments were subjected to analysis using independent t-test as well as paired sample t-test.

RESULT

Research Question One: What is the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students as compared between the experimental and control group?

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students when compared between the experimental and control group.

Table 1 independent t-test analysis of difference in effect of field trip on motivation of students as compared between the experimental and control groups.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. D	df	T	alpha	Sig	Result
Experimental Group	40	20.63	2.030	78	1.34	0.05	0.091	Insignificant (Reject H0)
Control Group	40	19.84	5.112					

Analysis in table 1 shows that participants in the experimental group had mean and standard deviation values were 20.63 and 2.03 while that of those in the control group were 19.84 and 5.11 respectively. Calculated t was 2.34 while sig value is 0.021. Hence, since sig ($p=0.091 > 0.05$) is greater than 0.05 alpha at 78 degrees of freedom, the null hypotheses is retained meaning that there is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students when compared between the experimental and control group.

Research Question Two: What is the effect of field trip on students’ academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on students’ academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores.

Table 2 independent t-test analysis of difference in effect of field trip on students’ academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. D	df	T	alpha	Sig	Result
Experimental Group	40	13.50	3.36	78	2.34	0.05	0.021	Significant (Reject H0)
Control Group	40	10.44	4.42					

Analysis in table 1 shows that participants in the experimental group had mean and standard deviation values were 13.50 and 3.36 while that of those in the control group were 10.44 and 4.43 respectively. Calculated t was 2.34 while sig value is 0.021. Hence, since sig ($p=0.021 < 0.05$) is less than 0.05 alpha at 78 degrees of freedom, the null hypotheses is rejected meaning that there is a significant difference in the effect of field trip on students’ academic performances when compared between the experimental and control group scores.

Research Question Three: Does field trip have any retention effect of field trip on students’ academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores?

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the retention effect of field trip on students’ academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and followup scores

Table 3: Showing paired-sample t-test analysis of retention effect of field trip on students’ academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores

Groups	Mean	Std. D	df	R	t	alpha	Sig	Result
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Posttest	13.50	1.36	39	0.102	0.95	0.05	5.021	Significant (Reject H0)
Follow-up Test	12.81	3.02						

From the analysis in table 3, mean and standard deviation score for the posttest remained 13.50 and 2.92 while follow up test had mean and standard deviation score of 12.81 and 3.02 respectively. From the mean values, it is seen that the performance of the students at the follow up stage dropped slightly compared to the posttest stage. This mean scores signifies that there is a positive effect of field trip on the performance of students in Civic Education. Again the relationship between the post test and the follow up test is 0.102. Calculated t was 0.95 while sig value was 5.021. Hence, since sig ($p=5.021 > 0.05$) is less than 0.05 alpha at 39 degrees of freedom, the hypotheses was retained meaning that There is no significant difference in the retention effect of field trip on students' academic performance in Civic Education as compared between the posttest and follow-up scores

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Finding one showed that there is no significant difference in the effect of field trip on academic motivation of students when compared between the experimental and control groups. The finding of "no significant difference in the effect of field trips on academic motivation of students" means that there is no statistically noticeable impact of field trips on students' academic motivation. The indication is that field trips may not be an effective tool for enhancing academic motivation. This means that other factors like teaching methods, curriculum, student interests) might have a stronger influence on academic motivation. On the other hand, it could be that feild trips might have other benefits apart but not specifically on academic motivation. However, this finding may come due to a number of reasons, it could be the design and methodology of the study, the sample size and population used, the measurement tools as well as the area of the study. it could also be that field trips might not be tailored to students' interests or learning needs, the trips might not be adequately integrated with classroom instruction as well as the inability of the measurement tools to capture the nuances of academic motivation. The finding of the study is in line with that as reported by Dimkpa and Okoro (2017) who reported a significant effect of experiential learning like field trip on academic motivation of students.

Table two reveled that there is a significant difference in the effect of field trip on academic achievement of students when compared between the experimental and control groups, the finding that there is a significant difference in the effect of field trips on academic achievement of students between the experimental and control groups means the difference in academic achievement between the experimental group (students who went on the field trip) and the control group (students who did not) is unlikely to occur by chance. The finding means that practically, field trips have a noticeable impact on academic achievement as those who participated in the field trip showed significantly better academic performance compared to those who did not. The finding of the study also means that field trips can be an effective supplement to traditional classroom instruction and that the field trip experience likely enhanced students' understanding, retention, and application of academic concepts. Finally, it could be that the difference in academic achievement might be attributed to factors such as hands-on learning experiences, real-world applications of abstract concepts, increased student engagement and motivation as well as improved teacher instruction and facilitation. The findings of the study is not surprising to the researchers because other researchers like Dasun, Ariya and Kazi (2023) had earlier reported significant difference in the academic performances of students that went on field trip and those in the control.

Finally, finding three showed that there is no significant difference in the retention effect of field trip on academic achievement of students when compared between their post-test and follow up test scores. This findings means that the difference in test scores between the post-test (immediately after the field trip) and follow-up test (after a period of time) is not statistically significant. This means that the field trip experience has a lasting impact on students' retention of academic knowledge. Students' test scores did not significantly decrease between the post-test and follow-up test. The field trip's effect on academic achievement will be sustained meaning that students can retain the information over time. The implication of this is that field trip is an effective tool for long-term knowledge retention although other instructional methods may be needed to reinforce learning and promote retention. It also implies that follow-up activities or reinforcement may be necessary to maintain learning gains. It is hence, noted that this should be used as a supplement to, not replacement for, traditional instruction. the findings of the study is not surprising to the researcher because it supports the findings of like Dasun, Ariya and Kazi (2023), Omosewo (2009) and Ganiya (2016) who all reported a a significant retention effect of field trips on students learning outcomes.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that educational implementers like teachers, governments as well as the school should re-evaluate field trip objectives and design to focus on motivation. They should incorporate interactive and engaging activities during field trips and also consider alternative strategies to boost motivation.
2. From finding two, it is recommended that stakeholders should integrate field trips into curriculum design. they should allocate resources to support field trip experiences. Train teachers to effectively integrate field trips with classroom instruction. they should as well investigate specific aspects of field trips (e.g., duration, frequency, content) to optimize effectiveness.
3. From finding three, it is recommended that teachers and proprietors should provide followup activities or reinforcement to promote retention. They should consider alternative strategies for promoting long-term retention (e.g., spaced repetition, interleaving. On a general note, stakeholders should conduct regular evaluations to assess effectiveness of field trips.

CONCLUSION

Field trips is a valuable supplement to traditional classroom instruction, enhancing academic achievement, but for it to be dependably effective, it long term retention effect should be monitored over time to ensure sustained academic motivation and achievement. By addressing these limitations and exploring new research directions, educators and policymakers can better understand the role of field trips in enhancing student learning outcomes.

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